

THE ROLE OF TOLERANCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY AND SOCIAL RELATIONS.

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Abstract. The article scientifically analyzes the conditions and laws of forming and raising the phenomenon of moral security and tolerance of youth.

Key words: Society, individual, spirituality, tolerance, humanity, right, freedom, duty, social life, spiritual life, strategy, idea, value, tradition, legitimacy, succession, inequality, coherence, relation.

Tolerance is a social value that has been deeply embedded in the human mentality since immemorial. Since ancient times, the evolution of consciousness and the development of philosophical ideas have played a significant role in the manifestation of spiritual factors in society. The emergence of many principles leading to social and spiritual stability in the relations between people in society brought out humanistic feelings. These principles have led to tolerant relations between people, and tolerance for different realities of social life. Over time, these processes created cultural values in society, strengthened the moral and social unity of the community, prevented various separations, and accelerated the pace of elimination of the causes leading to social chaos.

The sense of tolerance is an integral part of universal human values. In world practice, tolerance is characterized by the realization of a person's duty and responsibility to society, and the realization of a sense of respect for the law. Article 29 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that "Every person has a duty to society, only in this case can his personality be free and fully developed.

Every person should observe the limitations established by the law only to ensure that the rights and freedoms of others are sufficient and respected in a democratic society, to satisfy the fair requirements of morality, public order, and the general welfare in the exercise of their rights and freedoms”¹ expresses the principle of tolerance.

The principle of tolerance, characteristic of the nations of the world, exists in harmony with universal values. In particular, tolerance plays an important role in the social life of the people of the East. Tolerance was formed in the East mainly based on historical traditions, cultural heritage, and spiritual-social and religious-ethical rules, and it serves the development of the human relations system even in modern society. Thus, the tolerance of the peoples of the East is characterized by the belief in justice and humanity with a deep moral foundation, and the improvement of traditions that increase the spiritual and material well-being of a person

For example, the phenomenon of tolerance in the spiritual and social development of Chinese society was seriously influenced by Confucian ideas. The main principles of Confucian philosophy are based on the feelings of tolerance, which means "loving others"², which reflects the ideas of humanity, the harmony of human beings, nature and society, the actions of people and groups of people in society for the rights, needs and interests of each one, and solving social issues in public cooperation is important to achieve. The tradition of tolerance means that not only in China, but also in the social life of many eastern nations, it serves to strengthen the stability and perspective of the society.

In the West, the principle of tolerance is historically based on the idea of freedom, which has been combined over the years with the emergence of universal values related to the celebration of human rights, value and worth. In its development, it passed through a progressive stage based on the following sequence: "ancient property liberties, the struggle for religious freedom and, first of all, the

¹ Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Article 29. <https://constitution.uz/uz/pages/humanrights>.

² Confucius. The Analects / transl. by A. Waley. – Beijing : Press of Research and Teaching of Foreign Languages, 1998. – 78 c.

new churches, freedom of conscience, which was later recognized as the freedom of individuals, economic freedom based on secularization, the political power of the emerging bourgeoisie freedom and finally basic human rights declared in modern constitutions”³.

One of the important criteria for the development of the principle of tolerance in society is a high level of respect for spirituality, political and legal culture, norms, customs, laws, and regulations existing in society. For this reason, Article 48 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "Citizens are obliged to comply with the Constitution and laws, to respect the rights, freedoms, honor and dignity of other people."⁴ Therefore, the fact that legal culture, legal obligation, and legal responsibility are strengthened through legal documents is important in all respects.

In modern conditions, the current fast pace of globalization demands improvement of the human personality, their worldview, abilities with strengthening of spiritual factors. It is necessary to consider the factors of increasing the all-round responsibility of young people in social life in the efforts made in the system of raising the phenomenon of tolerance in the life of people, especially young people. This process expands their spiritual outlook, improves their intellectual ability, and increases their political and legal responsibility. This will serve to raise socially and politically mature young people with high morale, high cultural level, and create conditions for them to find their rightful place in life. Scientists say, "An enlightened society consists of enlightened individuals. Common sense and justice prevail in such a society. Such a society will be happy and prosperous. In a fair society, people's faith in the future and the incentive for creative work will be strong"⁵.

The tolerance that arises from the point of view of the formation of worldly consciousness develops step by step according to the characteristics of space and

³ Wieacker F. Foundations of European Legal Culture // The American Journal of Comparative Law. 1990 (Winter). Vol. 38. No. 1.

⁴ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, -Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2021. -P. 17.

⁵ Ibrohimov A., Sultanov H., Joraev N. A sense of homeland. -Tashkent, "Uzbekistan", 1996. -P. 357.

time. In a secular society, tolerance becomes a practical reality due to the recognition of its basic principles, which are interconnected with socio-cultural life. It is an important process to show tolerance of people regardless of their living conditions, social origin, work activities, cultural levels, ethnic and national characteristics. In these processes, tolerance emerges because of cultural development, high-level social thinking. "Tolerance in this case is a consequence of the totality of the social strategy and the result of a high culture. However, for a traditional society, the problem arises of human's ability to subordinate their feelings and interests to transcendental principles"⁶.

National growth of the people, achievement of high spirituality is the main goal of the improvement of every social life. Humanity has been progressing on a steady basis due to the progressive phenomenon of spiritual self-realization. The phenomenon of tolerance manifests itself differently in any historical period, space, and time, in different regions, in different nations and peoples. At the same time, tolerance is a phenomenon that occurs due to deep social relations and corresponds to the level of development of the nation, the state of stability of the society, and the spiritual development of the people.

Tolerance reflects the traditions of humanity, kindness, respect, hospitality, and benevolence that arise in the spiritual processes of society. N. Juraev said, "Regardless of nationality, race and worldview, the citizens of the country should have all the opportunities to meet their needs and lead their lives on the basis of voluntary choice. At the same time, they should contribute to maintaining a balance of stability in society, compromise and mutual understanding, approach arguments of the disputing parties with criteria of justice and create a general spirit of solidarity"⁷.

Tolerance as a social phenomenon is manifested in the activity of a person in the social processes of society, his initiative in mutual social dialogues, his active

⁶ Скворцов Л.В. Абсолютная истина и толерантность. Человек: образ и сущность- М.: Академия наук, 1998. - С. 17.

⁷ Joraev N. Spirituality is the savior of man and the world. -Tashkent, spirituality, 2018. -P. 20.

participation in solving the most critical issues of the state and society, and his reaction to spiritual processes. Based on such social relations, the characteristics of social tolerance are formed in a person, the principles of goodwill and mutual assistance to all positive processes in society are formed, and the characteristics of intolerance to negative events are formed. Also, it consists in timely elimination of social problems, focusing on solving the problem by state and society systems from the point of view of justice, giving effective suggestions aimed at ensuring the priority of people's interests.

It is social philosophy that calls for the understanding of the social and spiritual problems occurring in today's modern society and the active positive influence of people on them, the formation of the social, philosophical, and ideological foundations of human activity. An active approach to the issue of tolerance within the framework of social philosophy creates principles based on responsibility for the formation of a person's spiritual image, active attitude to living harmoniously, and cooperatively with others, and for choosing educational actions accordingly. These processes express the moral essence of tolerance and allow people to organize their spiritual activities on a stable basis.

The process of forming the tolerance of young people in the social and spiritual life of society relies on its own laws. These laws express the mechanisms, principles, and specific features of the formation of tolerance of young people and express the mutual relations and deep connection between people and various social systems in society. Laws related to the formation and development of youth tolerance include interrelatedness, succession, unevenness, coherence, repetition. So:

1. law of interrelationship: interrelationship of the phenomenon of youth tolerance with social, spiritual, political, legal, ecological systems in society;
2. law of succession: the process of passing down the phenomenon of youth tolerance from generation to generation;

3. the law of unevenness: the existence of the phenomenon of youth tolerance in society on an uneven basis in every space and time and its non-linear formation;
4. the law of integrity: the phenomenon of youth tolerance exists on an integral basis, there is a constant need for it;
5. law of repetition: the repetition of the main principles of tolerance in each period, the manifestation of its notable features in previous, present, and future times.

The existence of space and time-related changes in social life in society makes it important to control the main principles of the phenomenon of tolerance, ensuring constant manifestation. Public control plays a significant role in this issue and ensures the constant presence of the phenomenon of tolerance in social life. According to scientists, "The appearance of tolerance as a form of manifestation of opinions is closely related to the task of mass control of society's life. The way of mass control of changes in social life, according to its essence, consists of several appearances and forms"⁸.

Also, the issue of social regulation of the system of realizing the phenomenon of tolerance in social life, spiritual and educational life "can be conditionally classified as follows:

- a) the system of dialogues in the order of state offices and institutions, tolerance expressed in mutual relations and meetings, in particular, respect for colleagues and leaders-obedience, thoughtfulness;
- b) attitudes to the opinions expressed about everyday life, usual events, and events. Approaching issues with patience Expressing one's opinion thoughtfully;
- c) tolerance manifested in the family environment, in the circle of friends, in the circle of like-minded people. In particular, the manifestation of the

⁸ Kadirova Z. etc. Socio-philosophical issues of raising youth social activity and tolerance. - T.: Publishing House of the Institute of Philosophy and Law. 2006. - P. 144.

characteristics of not putting one's own interests first, not beating the character of others to the ground;

d) exchanges of ideas on social issues that occur during weddings and other such occasions. For example, manifestation of the characteristics of kindness, honesty, faith, sympathy, equality, insight, loyalty”⁹.

The sense of tolerance, which is one of the spiritual values of a person, is considered a process that creates cultural manifestations in the development of society and social relations, Q. Nazarov said:” human approach to humanity and tolerance in social life in communication with people, as a social being that reflects spiritual and moral aspects, is the main value in society. At the same time, he/she is also a general social being who has the characteristics of having a social attitude to the world, dealing with, and communicating with people, creating material and cultural wealth based on work, and expressing his/her thinking, feelings, and thoughts through language. Just as human cannot live without society, society cannot exist without humans”¹⁰.

The following conclusions were reached based on scientific analyzes related to the provision of the conditions for the formation and promotion of the phenomenon of tolerance and moral security of young people on a stable basis:

1. Tolerance plays a significant role in creating qualities related to the deep attitude of young people to the environment and society, to look at people with love, to respect them, to preserve the existing values and traditions in society and leave them to future generations.

2. Tolerance is important in ensuring the freedom and rights of young people as individuals, their activeness in the social and spiritual processes of society, and their responsible approach to the work of the country, people, and society.

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